

THERMAL COMFORT ASSESSMENT OF STATE UNIVERSITY BUILDINGS: A CASE OF CTU – MOALBOAL

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DEDICATION

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ABSTRACT

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This study, titled "Thermal Comfort Assessment of State University Buildings: A Case of CTU – Moalboal," investigates the critical issue of thermal comfort in classrooms within a four-storey building at Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus. The research aims to investigate how high temperatures and humidity influence students' perceptions of thermal comfort in their learning environment. Objective measurements, including temperature, humidity, and radiant temperature, were compared with ASHRAE Standard 55-2020 to assess the compliance of the indoor environment. Subjective responses were gathered from BSIE 1B students to determine their perceptions of thermal comfort. The study also aimed to identify the relationship between objective measurements and subjective perceptions, testing the hypothesis that there is a significant difference between these two parameters. Key findings reveal that neutral temperatures in naturally ventilated classrooms ranged from 28°C to 30°C, while air-conditioned spaces had a neutral range of 26°C to 27°C. Optimal temperatures for comfort were identified at 28°C for naturally ventilated environments and 25.5°C for air-conditioned settings, while acceptable temperature ranges varied between 28°C to 29°C and 26°C to 27°C, respectively. Despite interventions to improve thermal conditions, the study concluded that the efforts were ineffective in meeting the desired thermal comfort standards. Based on these findings, recommendations for improving thermal comfort and energy efficiency in similar educational settings are proposed.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Rationale

Thermal comfort is a critical aspect of indoor environmental quality that has significant implications for global climate concerns, building design, and occupant well-being. In classrooms, thermal comfort becomes especially important due to the high occupant density and its direct impact on student learning and performance. The discomfort resulting from inadequate thermal conditions can hinder cognitive function, concentration, and overall academic achievement (Mendell & Heath, 2005).

In fields such as architecture and engineering, designing indoor spaces that offer optimal thermal comfort remains an ongoing challenge. The American Society of Heating, Refrigerating, and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) has played a pioneering role in setting international standards for thermal comfort, particularly through the development of guidelines such as the ASHRAE Standard 55, which defines acceptable indoor thermal conditions for various building types (ASHRAE, 2010). These standards have influenced building practices worldwide, promoting a balance between occupant comfort and energy efficiency. The importance of thermal comfort extends beyond the physical. It aligns with broader sustainability goals, particularly in the context of urbanization and climate change. Building designs today must strike a balance between occupant comfort and energy conservation, reducing environmental impacts while maintaining high indoor air quality and thermal conditions (Bordass et al., 2001). The design and operation of indoor spaces must prioritize energy efficiency, particularly as global efforts intensify to curb energy consumption in

buildings, which account for nearly 40% of global energy use (“Energy Efficiency 2019,” 2019).

In the Philippines, a tropical climate with high temperatures and humidity poses unique challenges to maintaining thermal comfort in classrooms. The Philippine Green Building Code, developed by the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH), emphasizes sustainable building practices that aim to reduce energy consumption while enhancing indoor thermal comfort. This is vital in a country where reliance on air conditioning for cooling contributes to significant energy use and environmental degradation (Asiva Noor Rachmayani, 2015). Integrating natural ventilation and vegetation can significantly reduce energy consumption in tropical climates, highlighting the importance of these passive cooling strategies (Mughal and Beirão, 2019).

Moreover, the archipelagic nature of the Philippines introduces regional variations in climatic conditions, necessitating adaptable solutions that cater to the diverse thermal comfort needs of the population. By aligning national regulations with global standards like those set by ASHRAE, the Philippines continues to advance in its efforts to foster a sustainable and energy-efficient built environment.

In the case of Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus, the high occupant density combined with insufficient environmental controls presents a substantial challenge. Classrooms, especially those on the upper floors of multi-storey buildings, are more susceptible to heat gain due to direct exposure to sunlight and limited airflow. These conditions can lead to a thermal environment that not only impacts students' comfort but also hinders their cognitive performance, concentration, and overall well-being. According to the study of Wyon (n.d.) on the impact of

classroom indoor environmental quality, including thermal comfort, on students' academic performance, the study concluded that higher temperatures negatively affect cognitive functions, such as attention and information retention, leading to diminished academic outcomes. Studies have consistently shown that students perform better in thermally comfortable environments, with improved attention and retention of information.

The problem is amplified by the tropical climate in the Philippines, where classrooms frequently exceed comfort thresholds, particularly during midday and afternoon sessions. The thermal discomfort experienced by students in such environments is not merely an inconvenience; it can lead to fatigue, stress, and a significant decline in learning efficiency. A study by (Mendell and Heath, 2005) found that optimal thermal comfort contributes to better learning outcomes and overall academic success. Additionally, maintaining comfort levels solely through air conditioning in such environments is unsustainable, as it leads to increased energy consumption and operational costs for educational institutions. Therefore, addressing the thermal comfort of classrooms at Cebu Technological University is not just a matter of enhancing comfort but a pressing issue of improving learning outcomes, health, and institutional sustainability. This study seeks to investigate the effectiveness of existing classroom thermal conditions, both naturally ventilated and air-conditioned, in relation to ASHRAE standards, with the goal of identifying neutral and optimal temperature ranges for classrooms and recommending practical, energy-efficient solutions. The introduction of interventions, such as the use of 5mm insulation foam for windows, aims to create a balance between thermal comfort and energy efficiency, ultimately fostering a more conducive learning environment.

Theoretical Background

This research is based on Fanger's model of thermal comfort theory, adaptive thermal comfort theory based on ASHRAE 55-2020 standards.

Thermal comfort has a substantial impact on students' learning experiences and processes, with low thermal quality negatively influencing their mood and participation in educational spaces activities (Sakya and Primasetra, 2023). Majority of a modern man's time is spent indoors; comfort plays a big role in building design. Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) model, serves as a cornerstone in our understanding of thermal comfort. P.O. designed this model. Fanger acknowledges that a variety of elements influence thermal comfort, including air temperature, humidity, air speed, and human variables such as clothing insulation and metabolic rate. Fanger's predicted mean vote (PMV) model of thermal comfort, developed in the late 1960s, is used globally to quantify thermal comfort. Fanger's model was developed for usage under invariant environmental circumstances in air-conditioned rooms in moderate thermal temperature zones using college-aged students. Environmental engineering practice necessitates the development of a prediction strategy that can be used for all types of people in any type of building in any climate zone.

The PMV model established by P.O. Fanger is a well-known indicator for measuring thermal comfort using six parameters: ambient temperature, mean radiant temperature, relative humidity, air velocity, metabolic rate, and clothing insulation. Despite its popularity, precisely measuring these characteristics presents hurdles, resulting in differences in PMV estimates. Recent studies investigated modifications to the PMV model, including dimensionality reduction techniques utilizing machine learning, which obtained up to 89.70% accuracy (Park and Woo, 2023). The central

concept of this model is the Predicted Mean Vote (PMV), a numerical indicator that quantifies thermal comfort. It assigns values to the perceived level of comfort in a given location, so supporting designers and engineers in developing interior spaces that suit the comfort needs of their residents. Fanger's Model is important because it provides an organized, standardized technique to measuring and designing for thermal comfort. It permits the design of environments that promote well-being and productivity, in accordance with worldwide standards such as those established by ASHRAE.

The Adaptive Comfort Model suggests that indoor environments can be adjusted based on external conditions, particularly in naturally ventilated buildings, and thermal comfort levels can change based on individual experiences. This concept contradicts the traditional view of maintaining a steady thermal environment by pushing for temperature settings that are flexible based on individual preferences and external variables (Yang et al., 2024). Furthermore, the adaptive comfort model is less affected to variations in outdoor temperature, emphasizing the need for localized design solutions (Singh et al., 2023).

The American Society of Heating, Refrigerating, and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) is a respected authority on thermal comfort standards and HVAC system design. ASHRAE's recommendations, particularly ASHRAE Standard 55, serve as a global standard for evaluating and enhancing thermal comfort in a wide range of indoor situations, including residential, commercial, and institutional buildings. These guidelines provide architects, engineers, and building operators with a set of criteria and recommendations for creating indoor environments that improve occupant comfort and well-being.

Thermal comfort is vital in educational settings because it improves student attention, well-being, and academic success. The ASHRAE develops thermal comfort standards, such as ASHRAE 55-2020. These factors cover several variables, including temperature, humidity, airspeed, and garment insulation. Adherence to these principles is essential for building learning environments that support effective teaching and learning.

A complex combination of psychological, physiological, and environmental elements influences occupants' perceptions of thermal comfort (Rawal et al., 2022). According to the Adaptive Model, a well-established theory in the field of thermal comfort, individuals adapt to their thermal surroundings over time. This model recognizes that people's comfort levels might vary substantially within the same temperature range due to individual differences and flexibility. As a result, while measuring thermal comfort in educational settings, it is vital to consider occupant feedback and perceptions, as well as the role of adaptation in influencing comfort preferences. Thermal comfort is dependent on building ventilation systems. Proper ventilation affects both temperature regulation and air quality. An essential component of this research is determining the efficacy of current ventilation systems and their effects on thermal comfort. This insight will be beneficial in identifying areas for development and optimizing the use of existing systems.

The study emphasizes that occupants' feelings of thermal comfort are not static and can change over time as they respond to changing circumstances. It does this by utilizing Fanger's model of thermal comfort theory and the Adaptive Model in conjunction with ASHRAE 55-2020 criteria. While gathering information on occupant perceptions and examining the interactions between psychological factors—such as

adaptation—and objective measurements, this dynamic aspect of thermal comfort perception will be taken into consideration.

Figure 1. Theoretical framework

Review of Related Literature

In modern society setting, people spend most of their time indoors. Students spend more time at school than in any other building, highlighting the importance of providing comfortable indoor thermal conditions in these buildings. Thermal comfort field studies in classrooms were reported first in 1969 by Auliciem and vastly presented over the last decade. Indeed, about half of the addressed studies in the current paper have been conducted over the past five years (2011–2015), along with the raised awareness of energy efficiency issues in buildings (Zomorodian et al., 2016). These studies are primarily conducted in some parts of Asia and Europe in developed and developing countries with climate and cultural differences.

1. Educational Building and Thermal Comfort Studies

Educational buildings are a particular type of building with the prime objective of providing a conducive environment to promote teaching and learning (Barbhuiya & Barbhuiya, 2013; Mendell & Heath, 2005; Singh et al., 2019; Zomorodian et al., 2016). It is commonly recognized that educational systems involve different stages of learning where the students spend time depending on his/her age (ter Mors et al., 2011; Zomorodian et al., 2016). These different stages of learning are also categorized into different categories of classrooms: primary school rooms, secondary school rooms, and university school rooms (Singh et al., 2019). Although there are different categories in rooms, this review of related literature mainly focuses on thermal comfort studies in university classrooms.

1.1 Thermal Comfort Studies in University Classrooms

In the context of different educational levels, according to (Singh, 2019), the operation mode of the classroom is categorized into different modes of the classroom, there are following;

- (i) Naturally Ventilated (NV): A Classroom is constructed to operate under free running (FR) conditions 12 months a year.
- (ii) Air-conditioning (AC): A classroom is constructed with a heating and cooling system. During the study period, neither of the systems was switched on.

1.1.1 Natural Ventilated Classrooms

Adults between 19 and 26 comprise most students in naturally ventilated university classrooms. Students have more freedom to adjust their behaviors to manage or change the interior temperature settings at this age. In university classrooms used in NV/FR and air-conditioned mode, around 33 investigations have been conducted to determine the thermal comfort status. An investigation conducted by (Zhang et al., 2007) concluded that the PMV/PPD model overestimates students' thermal comfort and that the impact of humidity on thermal comfort is only apparent at higher temperatures. Additionally, the desirable temperature climate of university classrooms in Nevada is influenced by external environmental conditions. Corgnati et al. (2009) discovered that students preferred a warm atmosphere in the winter. After conducting a questionnaire-based study on thermal comfort throughout the spring in a warm and humid climate, (Baruah et al., 2014) found that the individuals did not experience severe levels of thermal discomfort. This study also considers "adaptation" and concludes that during the winter months, a person can feel comfortable at temperatures between 22 and 23.5 °C and during the summer, between 27.3 and 30.7 °C. The significant variance in clothing patterns in both seasons has been found to justify the respondent's behavioral, physiological, and psychological adaptation. Additionally, it was shown that various adaptable methods, such as using fans or

closing or opening windows, are frequently employed (Mishra et al., 2017); Mishra & Ramgopal, 2015).

The adaptive thermal comfort principle mentions the relationship between controls, adaptive behavior, and thermal comfort. To investigate this connection, Nico et al. conducted research in which they discovered that improving microclimate management and the adaptability of adaptive activities, such as adjusting garment level and opening windows, positively influence the sensation of contentment with indoor environmental conditions. The investigation also concluded that most items reported a chilly thermal feeling, preferred a warmer environment in winter and a warm thermal sensation, and chose a more relaxed one in summer (Nicol & Humphreys, 2002).

1.1.2 Air-conditioned Classrooms

A decade ago, studies on measuring thermal comfort in university classrooms began. According to (Hwang et al., 2006) air temperature, air movement, and mean radiant temperature all substantially affect students' thermal feelings. In contrast, humidity has no statistically significant effect. The study also reveals that female students quickly shift their clothing levels in response to changes in interior temperature and have a shorter neutral temperature range. In their studies, (Zhang et al., 2007) found that the neutral temperature in a classroom differs from that in a lab, which brought functionality into the picture. In the lab, compared to the classroom, the responders were more sensitive to temperature fluctuation. While the figure was close to 6 °C in the classroom, a gradient of around one sensation unit every 3-4 °C was detected in the laboratory (3 °C in summer and 4 °C in winter). According to (Zaki et al., 2017) study on Malaysian students, there are often few opportunities for outside-of-class activities. Therefore, people have few alternatives for adapting to the indoor

thermal environment. In hot, humid locations where a higher level of heat tolerance may be present in the general population, the existing guidelines for HVAC buildings may potentially underestimate inhabitants' thermal preferences.

A study by (Buratti & Ricciardi, 2009) sought to determine the relationships between PMV and the difference between equivalent uniform temperature (T_{eu}) and uniform comfort temperature (T_u), as well as the relationship between PPD and the absolute of ($T_{eu} - T_u$). (Jung et al., 2011) also made an intriguing adaptation-related conclusion that students readily accept slightly cool but not easily warm environments. This study confirmed the Fanger hypothesis, which predicts a null value of PMV in neutral comfort settings, by finding a linear connection between PMV and $T_{eu} - T_u$. Buildings with air conditioning are being designed with low Air Change per Hour (ACH) rates to meet the energy efficiency demand (Liu et al., 2011; Mishra & Ramgopal, 2015) However, this approach does not work in schools with higher occupancy. According to research, IEQ and IAQ must be given sufficient consideration when building air-conditioned classrooms since they affect students' capacity to study (Liu et al., 2011). By raising the airflow supply from 10 to 15 ACH at the higher interior conditions of 26.8 °C, 27.3 °C, and 26.4 °C, the thermal satisfaction acceptance % in stratum ventilation methods may be increased (Mishra et al., 2017; Mishra & Ramgopal, 2015).

High vertical temperature differences must be avoided when developing the ventilation system for air-conditioned classrooms (Liu et al., 2011) Non-classroom variables, including visibility, acoustics, and furnishings, have an impact on students' perceptions of their learning in the classroom as well (Liu et al., 2011). Additionally, it was discovered that students are not very satisfied with acoustics and artificial lighting. While enhancing acoustics has increased learning, boosting artificial illumination has

little effect (Barbhuiya & Barbhuiya, 2013) Building standards require insulation materials when designing classrooms in cold climates. However, the rising use of ICT in university education systems necessitates a pre-design evaluation of heat generated by this equipment.

Students in university courses have more freedom to take on adaptive activities to restore their comfort. According to a study relating controls, adaptive actions, and thermal comfort, students are more satisfied with the interior thermal environment when there is greater control over the microclimate and adaptive activities. Students in both non-air-conditioned and air-conditioned classrooms favored a cold experience here. Therefore, lowering the fixed temperature during the winter when the heating system is required to run will result in a 12% reduction in heating energy usage (Jung et al., 2011). University students enter and exit the classroom at the end of each class. Therefore, if a class lasts an hour, they are in a transitory state for roughly 20 to 30 percent of the time. Therefore, students' thermal comfort and preferences in university classrooms are significantly influenced by their memories of the previous setting. Throughout their tenure at the institution, this occurs frequently throughout the day. When ISO 7730, ASHRAE 55, and CEN 15251 standards, which typically deal with steady-state conditions, are applied to evaluate thermal classroom environments, the deviation reported by many studies seems obvious (Hwang et al., 2006; Zheng et al., 2020). However, students experience a transient thermal condition for the first 15-20 minutes of class.

Earlier studies have been conducted at educational institutions at many levels and even in universities. However, each of these earlier studies was distinct in terms of the research technique used and the characteristics of the study's sample. For instance, ventilation options were not specified in any of the investigations. However, hardly any

university buildings rely only on natural ventilation, even though most studies on adaptable thermal comfort focused on naturally ventilated buildings. A Thermal comfort study may determine how people feel within a structure and this method requires understanding the adaptive behavior and thermal preferences of inhabitants in developing nations compared to industrialized countries, which display more ecologically friendly energy use under identical climatic circumstances.

As for all the factors influencing thermal comfort, indoor air temperature is subject to considerable variation. As well as differing depending on the time of day, there are vertical and horizontal temperature gradients within a room at any one time. And, within a dwelling, ambient temperatures will vary from room to room depending on their use and orientation. As well as the ambient temperature, thermal comfort will be affected by heat sources and colder surfaces within the dwelling, and by the season and the local climate

Growing awareness of the health risks associated with sedentary behavior have raised concerns about health and safety of office workers who spend as much as 77% of their work hours sedentary and often for prolonged periods. According to (Van Kasteren et al., 2019) on the research about thermal comfort and physical activity in office setting, shows the relationship between physical activity and thermal activity is warranted, using data from building management systems to capture data not only temperature but other measures of thermal comfort such as humidity and air flow.

A study stated that when people are not satisfied with the indoor environment, effects on the comfort, health, and productivity of these occupants are notice (Al horr et al., 2016) and implied of lack of environmental comfort causes occupants to spend energy and attention trying to make up for this lack of comfort instead of focusing on their main activity. Studies have analyzed the link between performance and thermal

comfort of occupants in the workplace with considerable results on the levels of productivity (Li et al., 2020). In addition, lack of thermal comfort results in environmental stress producing a negative performance on workplace (Nico et al., 2015).

A comfortable indoor environment can effectively reduce the occupants' complaints and improve work productivity, which is of great importance in promoting economic development. Among these factors, thermal comfort has the greatest influence in occupants' comfort and productivity (Al horr et al., 2016). (Bueno et al., 2021) reveals on their study that it is necessary to ascertain how environmental variables (air temperature, average radiant temperature, air velocity and relative air humidity) and people (metabolism and clothing) influence thermal comfort and productivity.

A report, entitled 'The Physiological Basis for Health Standards for Dwellings', includes a section on the thermal environment, and it is this that provided the basis for subsequent WHO guidance on the indoor air temperature range necessary to protect health, including the health of those more likely to be susceptible to high and low temperatures (Ormandy & Ezratty, 2012).

According to (Chua et al., 2016) the issue of workers comfort in offices and workspace quality in a Low Energy Office (LEO) building. New energy efficient building concepts and technologies require a revision of comfort standards, to create a suitable thermal condition in avoiding occupant dissatisfaction, adverse effect on their productivity and overall building performance (Chua et al., 2016). Thermal comfort was measured by the number of employees complaining of thermal discomfort (Shaharon & Jalaludin, 2012). Frequent changes in arrangement in office space and the huge

amount of the cables brought about by the extensive use of computers make the implementation of air conditioning office a necessity (Haynes, 2008). Naturally ventilated building designs can perform efficiently in a hot climate country like Malaysia because of their low evaporation rate, long hours of sunshine, high relative humidity and very overcast cloud cover. As a country that is progressing towards an energy consumption conscious target, buildings are designed to enable natural ventilation (Sakiyama et al., 2020). Results of a study in Germany, which was conducted on workplace occupant satisfaction in 16 office buildings revealed that the occupants' control of the indoor climate and moreover the perceived effect of their intervention strongly influences their satisfaction with the thermal indoor quality (Wagner et al., 2007). To enable a researcher to improve the thermal comfort in the workplace, the six parameters contributing to thermal comfort were measured and calculated using Fanger (1970) comfort model. This model which was based on Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) and Predicted Percentage Dissatisfied people (PPD) index and used of BS EN ISO 7730 and BS EN ISO 10551 British standards are recommended (Marigo et al., 2023). The study on thermal comfort emphasize the importance of thermal comfort for office occupants and highlight that achieving thermal comfort in offices not only delivers more satisfaction for the occupants, but also improves their performance (Shaharon & Jalaludin, 2012).

Studies on indoor climate in educational spaces reveal significant insights into air quality, ventilation strategies, and their impact on user performance. Study indicates that effective air distribution methods, such as displacement ventilation, enhance indoor climate conditions, particularly in classrooms, by maintaining low air velocities and uniform thermal conditions (Zhao et al., 2022). Moreover, there has been a growing focus on natural ventilation strategies, particularly in the aftermath of

COVID-19, highlighting the importance of sufficient air renewal to reduce the spread of airborne diseases (Aguilar et al., 2023). In hot climates, the interaction between noise, temperature, and humidity is vital for sustaining indoor environmental quality (IEQ), with statistical models aiding in the prediction of these factors (Al-Isawi et al., 2022). Additionally, research indicates that a healthy inside environment requires good indoor air quality, which has a substantial impact on human health and well-being. It can reduce absenteeism; improve test scores, and increase student/teacher learning/teaching productivity (Sadrizadeh et al., 2022).

Studies on outdoor climate in educational spaces reveal significant impacts on thermal comfort and overall well-being of students. Research indicates that vegetation plays a crucial role in mitigating thermal stress, particularly in hot climates. For instance, a study in Riyadh demonstrated that strategically placed trees can reduce air temperature by up to 3.2°C and mean radiant temperature by over 64°C (Binabid & Anteet, 2023). Similarly, an assessment in Andalusia highlighted that most schools have inadequate shaded areas, with 90% containing less than 10% wooded space (Serrano-Jiménez et al., 2021). In humid-hot regions like Guangzhou, children's thermal comfort was closely linked to air temperature and vegetation preferences, suggesting that bioclimatic designs can enhance outdoor spaces (Guo et al., 2023). Furthermore, sensory design in university campuses under hot-humid climates can improve outdoor experiences (Fan et al., 2020). These findings underscore the necessity for thoughtful design and vegetation integration in educational environments to promote comfort and health.

THE PROBLEM

Statement of the Problem

This research seeks to address the critical issue of thermal comfort in classrooms within a four-storey building at Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus. The study aims to investigate how high temperatures and humidity influence students' perceptions of thermal comfort in their learning environment while gathering objective measurements through physical assessment methods. The focus will be on students' levels of satisfaction and comfort in relation to the thermal conditions they experience.

Specifically, this study seeks to determine and assess:

1. What are the classroom temperature conditions based on objective measurements, and how do they compare to ASHRAE standards 55-2020?
2. How do occupants perceive the level of thermal comfort in classrooms?
3. How does the objective measurement of thermal comfort in educational environments relate to the subjective perceptions of students?

H0: There is no significant relationship between the objective measurements and the perception of students.

H1: There is a significant relationship between the objective measurements and the perception of students.

4. What are the neutral and optimal temperatures, along with the acceptable temperature range, in the state university (CTU-MOALBOAL)?
5. What are the possible recommendations/ policies can be done?

Significance of the Study

This study is beneficial to the following entities:

Students – Beneficial to the student's physical health and well-being since maintaining a comfortable temperature range can help students feel more at ease and promotes better overall health. Moreover, the thermal comfort impacts student's productivity and efficiency because when students are in a comfortable environment, they can study efficiently, complete the task faster and retain the lessons better.

University/Institutions – Prioritizing thermal comfort can contribute to energy efficiency and sustainability efforts of universities and schools. By optimizing building design, ventilation systems, insulation, and cooling technologies to ensure thermal comfort, educational institutions can reduce energy consumption, lower greenhouse gas emissions, and contribute to a more sustainable campus. This aligns with the growing emphasis on environmentally responsible practices and resource conservation. Ensuring thermal comfort in educational facilities is essential to comply with building codes, regulations, and standards related to indoor environmental quality. Adhering to these guidelines demonstrates the commitment of universities and schools to providing a safe and healthy learning environment for their students and staff.

Teachers and Faculty Members – Comfortable working conditions can positively impact their well-being, job satisfaction, and performance. When educators are in a comfortable environment, they can focus more effectively on teaching, engage with students, and deliver their lessons with greater efficiency.

Academe and Researchers - Researching thermal comfort contributes to the understanding of human physiological and psychological responses to thermal conditions. It allows researchers to investigate the complex interactions between environmental factors, human perception, and comfort. By expanding the body of knowledge on thermal comfort, researchers contribute to the scientific understanding of human comfort and well-being.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Method

In this study, both objective physical measurement and subjective judgements was utilized. Occupants were requested to complete a thermal comfort questionnaire while spot measurements of the interior variables were obtained. Physical measurements were carried out in the classroom, the following factors are considered with respect to ASHRAE Standard 55 -2020.

- i. Air Temperature
- ii. Radiant Temperature
- iii. Humidity

In addition to the physical measurements, subjective measurement guided by ASHRAE 55 Standards was also utilized, in which were administered simultaneously with the physical measurements in the class.

Flow of the Study

Figure 2. Flowchart

Research Environment

The research was conducted at a four-story building, notably on the fourth level, in Moalboal, Cebu, on the campus of Cebu Technological University - Moalboal Campus. The facility under inquiry was a typical structure found in educational institutions, including classrooms, offices, and social areas. One specific classroom was selected. The selection of this specific habitat was deliberate, with the goal of capturing thermal comfort difficulties encountered in a real-world situation, where multiple activities and occupant preferences intersect.

Figure 3. Map of Moalboal

Figure 4. Map of Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus

Figure 5. Four-storey Building

Figure 6: Classroom under investigation

Respondents

This study specifically target students as the primary occupants of the classroom environments under investigation. The selected sample consisted of 31 students (natural ventilated classroom & air-conditioned classroom) Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering 1B of Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus was selected. The respondents are the occupant of the fourth floor. By focusing solely on students, the research accurately gauged the thermal experiences of the individuals most directly affected by the classroom conditions. This approach ensured that the data collected was relevant and applicable to the study's objectives.

Figure 7: BSIE 1B Students in NV and AC have an open dress code.

Instrument

The study utilized survey questionnaires instrument specifically, point-in-time questionnaire to assess and determined the perceptions of the respondents. The researchers utilized survey questionnaires guided by the ASHRAE 55 as one of the data collection instruments for this study with questions aimed at eliciting relevant information concerning the occupants' experiences towards thermal comfort in classroom as well as the factors affecting the students' overall performance and well – being in Cebu Technological University -Moalboal Campus.

Moreover, the study utilized instruments such as thermometer or temperature sensors to measure air temperature, infrared thermometers was utilized to capture the temperature of surfaces directly impacting the students' comfort, thereby assessing the radiant temperature, and lastly, hygrometers measured the humidity levels, which significantly influenced the overall thermal experience of the occupants.

DIGITAL HYGRO – THERMOMETER

INFRARED THERMOMETER

Figure 8: Physical Instruments

Data Gathering Procedure

I. Objective Physical Measurements:

To obtain precise and reliable measurements, the study employed calibrated instruments that adhere to industry standards. This includes the use of calibrated thermometers or temperature sensors to measure air temperature at strategic points within each classroom. Similarly, infrared thermometers were utilized to capture the temperature of surfaces directly impacting the students' comfort, thereby assessing the radiant temperature. Additionally, hygrometer was used measure humidity levels, which significantly influence the overall thermal experience of the occupants.

Before the students' arrival, the research team strategically position measurement instruments in various locations within each classroom. This positioning ensures a comprehensive representation of the thermal conditions. The instruments record air temperature, radiant temperature, and humidity, generating a dataset that accurately portrays the thermal environment.

II. Subjective Measurements:

In parallel with the objective measurements, the students (31 in total) were engaged in providing their subjective feedback through a thermal comfort questionnaire. This questionnaire was structured around established scales, such as the Thermal Sensation Scale and the Thermal Preference Scale, in accordance with ASHRAE Standard 55-2020. The questionnaire was designed to elicit information about the students' perceptions of their own comfort levels and their preferences concerning the thermal conditions in their respective classrooms.

Students participating in the study were briefed on the research's aims and the procedures involved. At the start of a class session, students receive the thermal comfort questionnaire. This questionnaire probes their perceptions of thermal sensations and preferences within their current classroom environment. By completing the questionnaire anonymously, students can provide candid responses, further enhancing the reliability of the collected subjective data.

Statistical Treatment

Descriptive statistics was used to summarize the objective measurements, elucidating the thermal conditions of classroom. Furthermore, statistical analyses, such as Pearson's Correlation Coefficients and Significance of Correlation were employed to explore the potential relationships between the objective measurements and the subjective responses provided by the students. This comprehensive analysis provides valuable insights into the alignment between objective measurements and the students' comfort perceptions.

Definition of Terms

Thermal Comfort - refers to the comfort level experienced by occupants in indoor spaces, particularly in educational buildings, and is influenced by factors such as temperature, humidity, air speed, and clothing choices.

ASHRAE Standard 55-2020 - serves as a global reference point for evaluating and improving thermal comfort, providing criteria and recommendations for architects, engineers, and building operators.

Fanger's Model of Thermal Comfort - is a fundamental theoretical framework used in the study to understand and assess thermal comfort in indoor environments.

Adaptive Thermal Comfort Theory - The study applies the Adaptive Thermal Comfort Theory based on ASHRAE 55-2020 standards to account for the dynamic nature of thermal comfort perceptions.

Ventilation Systems - The study emphasizes the importance of evaluating the efficacy of current ventilation systems in educational buildings to understand their impact on thermal comfort.

Indoor Climate – refers to the environmental conditions within a building, specifically thermal comfort, humidity, air quality, and lighting.

Outdoor Climate – refers to the weather outside of a structure, taking into account elements like temperature, humidity, wind direction, and sun exposure. Geographical location, seasonal variations, and weather patterns all have an impact.

Objective Measurements – is a quantifiable and empirical assessment of environmental parameters such as temperature, surface temperature, humidity, and airflow that provides solid, data-driven insight into classroom thermal conditions.

Subjective Measurements – refers to students' perceptual evaluations of thermal comfort, notably in the classroom.

Thermal Sensation Vote (TSV) – A subjective rating given by occupants on how they perceive the temperature, typically measured on a 7-point scale from cold (-3) to hot (+3).

Thermal Preference Scale – A scale used to measure occupants' thermal sensation or preference, often ranging from "too cold" to "too warm."

Thermal Acceptability – The percentage of occupants, who find the indoor environment thermally acceptable, typically based on subjective comfort surveys.

Operative Temperature – A measure that accounts for both air temperature and mean radiant temperature, representing the combined thermal effect felt by occupants.

CHAPTER 2

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Classroom Conditions

Indoor Climate based on Physical Measurements

The summary statistics for indoor classroom climate variables observed during classroom visits at 10:00 a.m. and 3:00 p.m. are presented in Table 1. The measured air and radiant temperatures in naturally ventilated classrooms were consistently at 29°C during the morning (10:00 a.m.) and increased slightly to 30°C in the afternoon (3:00 p.m.). This gradual rise in temperature reflects the influence of external environmental conditions on the indoor climate, particularly the lack of mechanical cooling interventions in naturally ventilated spaces. In contrast, air-conditioned classrooms demonstrated a more stable thermal environment, with air temperatures recorded at 26°C and radiant temperatures at 28°C during the morning. By the afternoon, the temperature slightly increases at 27°C and radiant temperature at still 28°C. The narrow range of temperature variation within air-conditioned classrooms underscores the effectiveness of HVAC systems in maintaining a controlled indoor climate, mitigating the fluctuations typically observed in naturally ventilated spaces. This thermal environment is very similar to the one recorded in the study "Thermal Comfort Analyses of Secondary School Students in the Tropics" (Baharuddin Hamzah, 2018). The classroom conditions of the examined secondary schools exhibit hot thermal environments. The indoor air temperature ranged from 28.2°C to 33.6°C, with an average of 30.8°C, exceeding the thermal comfort zone defined in the ASHRAE 55 standard and in a naturally ventilated secondary school in Singapore (Wong, 2003).

Relative humidity levels further illustrate the differences between the two environments. In naturally ventilated classrooms, the relative humidity was recorded at 67% in the morning and slightly decreased to 66% by the afternoon. These values indicate a relatively high moisture content in the air, which could contribute to a perception of discomfort among occupants, especially as temperatures rise. On the other hand, air-conditioned classrooms maintained lower humidity levels, with measurements of 58% in the morning and a slight increase to 60% in the afternoon. The reduced humidity in these environments likely contributed to a more comfortable and perceived cooler atmosphere, despite the minor temperature increase. This controlled humidity was crucial in preventing the indoor air from feeling overly humid or stuffy, which was often a challenge in naturally ventilated spaces.

Table 1. Summary of Indoor Climate

Summary of indoor climate

		Naturally Ventilated							
		Mean		S.D.		Min.		Max.	
		10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00
One classroom visit									
31 occupants total									
Air Temperature (°C)		29	30	0.7	0.9	28.2	28.8	29.6	30.6
MRT (°C)		29	30	0.5	0.7	28.5	29.1	29.5	30.4
Relative Humidity (%)		67	66	3.5	2.9	62.5	64.1	69	69.2
		Air-conditioned							
		Mean		S.D.		Min.		Max.	
		10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00
One classroom visit									
31 occupants total									
Air Temperature (°C)		26	27	0.3	1.8	26.4	26.5	26.7	30
MRT (°C)		28	28	0.2	0.6	27.4	27.5	28	28.7
Relative Humidity (%)		58	60	3.1	5.5	55.5	56	61.5	65.8

Outdoor Climate based on Physical Measurements

The summary statistics for outdoor classroom climate variables, as observed during visits at 10:00 a.m. and 3:00 p.m., are detailed in Table 2. The measured air and radiant temperatures in naturally ventilated classrooms were consistent at 28°C during the morning (10:00 a.m.) but showed a significant increase to 31°C by the afternoon (3:00 p.m.). This increase in temperature aligns with the expected diurnal pattern of warming, particularly in outdoor or semi-outdoor environments, where direct solar radiation and ambient temperature contribute to the rise in thermal conditions throughout the day. In air-conditioned classrooms, the morning temperatures were recorded at 29°C for both air and radiant measurements. However, by the afternoon, these temperatures surged to 36°C and 38°C, respectively. The stark contrast between the morning and afternoon temperatures in air-conditioned environments suggests a potential issue with the thermal regulation within the classrooms. The substantial rise in both air and radiant temperatures could indicate that the cooling systems were either overwhelmed by the external heat load or were not functioning optimally to counterbalance the afternoon heat.

Relative humidity levels also revealed distinct patterns between naturally ventilated and air-conditioned classrooms. In naturally ventilated spaces, humidity was recorded at 69% in the morning, dropping to 61% by the afternoon. This decline in humidity coincides with the temperature increase, reflecting a typical response where higher temperatures often correlate with lower relative humidity as the air's capacity to hold moisture increases. Conversely, in air-conditioned classrooms, the relative humidity started at 68% in the morning and dropped significantly to 53% in the afternoon. Lower humidity enhanced comfort yet excessively high temperatures may

negate this benefit, leading to an environment that feels uncomfortably warm despite the lower moisture content in the air.

Table 2. Summary of Outdoor Climate

Summary of outdoor climate

One classroom visit 31 occupants total	Naturally Ventilated							
	Mean		S.D.		Min.		Max.	
	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00
Air Temperature (°C)	28	31	0.8	0.7	27.7	30.5	29.5	32
MRT (°C)	28	31	0.6	0.8	27.4	30.1	28.5	31.7
Relative Humidity (%)	69	61	0.8	1	68	60	70	62
One classroom visit 31 occupants total	Air-conditioned							
	Mean		S.D.		Min.		Max.	
	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00
Air Temperature (°C)	29	36	0.9	3	28	31	30	39
MRT (°C)	29	38	0.8	3.2	28.5	32	30.2	40.5
Relative Humidity (%)	68	53	2.4	10.4	65	41	71	66

The data presented in the table 3 illustrates the differences in air temperature, radiant temperature, and relative humidity between indoor and outdoor environments under varying conditions. In naturally ventilated classrooms, these differences were minimal, indicating that the indoor climate closely mirrored the outdoor conditions. This similarity suggests that naturally ventilated spaces are more susceptible to external environmental fluctuations, offering limited control over the indoor climate. Consequently, occupants in these spaces are more likely to experience the same thermal conditions as those prevailing outside, which could impact their comfort and adaptability.

In contrast, air-conditioned classrooms exhibited a moderate difference between indoor and outdoor climate variables, reflecting a more controlled and regulated indoor environment. The air conditioning systems effectively moderated the

indoor climate, reducing the direct influence of external conditions. This ability to maintain a distinct indoor environment demonstrates the effectiveness of air-conditioned classrooms in providing a more stable and comfortable setting for occupants. The moderate difference in air temperature, MRT, and relative humidity suggests that while the air-conditioned spaces are not entirely isolated from the outdoor climate, they offer a significant improvement in thermal comfort compared to naturally ventilated spaces.

Table 3. Difference between Indoor and Outdoor Climate

Summary of difference of indoor and outdoor climate

	Naturally Ventilated		Air – conditioned	
	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00
Air Temperature (°C)	1	-1	-3	-9
MRT (°C)	1	-1	-1	-10
Relative Humidity (%)	-2	5	-10	7

COMPARISON OF PHYSICAL MEASUREMENT TO THE ASHRAE – 55 STANDARDS

I. PMV MODEL (*air – conditioned*)

✓ Complies with ASHRAE Standard 55-2023

PMV = 0.45
Sensation = Neutral

PPD = 9 %
SET = 26.5 °C

Psychrometric (air temperature)

✗ Does not comply with ASHRAE Standard 55-2023

PMV = 0.69
Sensation = Slightly Warm

PPD = 15 %
SET = 27.1 °C

Psychrometric (air temperature)

Figure 9. PMV Model (*morning on the left and afternoon on the right*)

The objective measurements reveal a clear distinction in thermal comfort between the morning and afternoon conditions in the air-conditioned classroom, as assessed against the ASHRAE Standard 55. During the morning session, the classroom temperature was 27°C, with a PMV of 0.45 and a PPD of 9%. These values align with the ASHRAE 55 standard comfort criteria, indicating that the majority of occupants are likely to experience thermal comfort within this environment. The stability in temperature and humidity control during the morning suggests that the HVAC system is functioning effectively to maintain conditions within the acceptable comfort range. However, by the afternoon, the thermal conditions in the air-conditioned classroom deteriorate slightly. The temperature rises to 28°C, with the PMV increasing to 0.69 and the PPD to 15%. These figures exceed the ASHRAE recommended limits,

signaling a notable decline in thermal comfort. A PMV of 0.69 suggests that the indoor environment is approaching a level of warmth that could cause discomfort for many occupants, while the PPD of 15% indicates that over one-fifth of the occupants may feel thermally uncomfortable. This shift from comfort to discomfort underscores the challenges of maintaining consistent thermal conditions throughout the day, particularly during peak heat periods when the external thermal load is higher.

II. ADAPTIVE MODEL (*naturally ventilated*)

NV 10:00

✓ Complies with ASHRAE Standard 55-2023

80% acceptability limits = Operative temperature: 23.0 to 30.0 °C

Comfortable

90% acceptability limits = Operative temperature: 24.0 to 29.0 °C

Too warm

Adaptive chart

NV 3:00

✓ Complies with ASHRAE Standard 55-2023

80% acceptability limits = Operative temperature: 23.9 to 30.9 °C

Comfortable

90% acceptability limits = Operative temperature: 24.9 to 29.9 °C

Too warm

Adaptive chart

Figure. 10. Adaptive Comfort Model

ASHRAE Standard 55 Standard uses prevailing mean outdoor temperature is greater than 10°C (50°F) and less than 33.5°C (92.3°F) lines to delineate the temperature boundaries of the comfort zone on the psychometric chart. Compliance to the standard given these seats of conditions was poor for naturally ventilated

classrooms, but was as expected for air-conditioned and also to the with intervention classrooms (ASHRAE, 2020).

According to the ASHRAE 55-2020 adaptive comfort model, the acceptable indoor temperature range is determined by the prevailing mean outdoor temperature, using a linear relationship to define the comfort zone (Tartarini et al., 2020). This model accounts for the adaptive nature of human thermal comfort, which allows occupants to adjust to varying indoor temperatures based on their recent thermal experiences and expectations. The adaptive comfort chart from ASHRAE 55-2020 illustrates that for a prevailing mean outdoor temperature of 28°C, the 80% acceptability limit for indoor operative temperatures typically ranges from approximately 23°C to 30°C. This range reflects the temperatures at which at least 80% of occupants are expected to find the environment thermally comfortable without needing mechanical cooling. Similarly, when the prevailing mean outdoor temperature rises to 31°C, the acceptable indoor operative temperature narrows slightly, ranging from approximately 24°C to 29°C.

Applying the ASHRAE 55 standards to the observed data, we find that in the morning, when the prevailing mean outdoor temperature was 28°C, the operative temperature of 29°C within the naturally ventilated classroom was in compliance with the ASHRAE 55 guidelines. Under the 80% acceptability limits, this environment was considered "*comfortable*," as it fell within the acceptable range of 23°C to 30°C. However, when assessed against the more stringent 90% acceptability limits, where the acceptable operative temperature range is between 24°C and 29°C, the environment was deemed "*too warm*," as it did not fully meet the comfort criteria. Similarly, in the afternoon, with the prevailing outdoor temperature rising to 31°C, the operative temperature inside the classroom reached 30°C, still within compliance with

the ASHRAE 55 standard. Under the 80% acceptability limits, this temperature was also considered "*comfortable*," as it fell within the range of 23.9°C to 30.9°C. However, under the 90% acceptability limits, where the operative temperature range is between 24.9°C and 29.9°C, the classroom environment was again classified as "*too warm*" and did not meet the stricter comfort threshold.

Therefore, the indoor environment in both the morning and afternoon sessions of the naturally ventilated classroom meets the ASHRAE 55 standard and is considered within the comfort zone under the 80% acceptability limits. However, it does not meet the 90% acceptability limits, indicating that while the space remains thermally acceptable, there are moments when occupants may feel slightly warm.

SUBJECTIVE MEASUREMENT RESULTS

Figure. 11. Frequency of thermal sensation responses in naturally ventilated and air – conditioned classroom

Figure 11 illustrates the distribution of subjective assessments of indoor climates, specifically the frequency of thermal sensation responses provided by occupants. At 10:00 a.m., the mean comfort vote for occupants in naturally ventilated classrooms was neutral (0), indicating that the majority of occupants perceived the thermal environment as neither uncomfortable nor comfortable. This neutrality suggests that the naturally ventilated spaces were generally perceived as stable in terms of thermal conditions, with no significant deviations from comfort. In contrast, the air-conditioned classroom exhibited a mean comfort vote of slightly cool (-1) at the same time, reflecting a predominant perception of the indoor climate as "slightly cool." This indicates that the air-conditioned environment was perceived as significantly cooler than the naturally ventilated space, which could imply that the temperature settings or cooling effects in the air-conditioned classroom were more intense, leading

to a preference for cooler conditions among the occupants. The discrepancy in comfort votes between the two types of classrooms highlights the varying thermal preferences and environmental perceptions of occupants based on the type of ventilation and temperature control employed.

Figure. 12. Thermal acceptability based on ASHRAE thermal sensation of the central three categories (-1, 0, +1)

The observed results indicate a near adherence to ASHRAE's 80% thermal acceptability criterion across different conditions. Specifically, in naturally ventilated spaces, the thermal acceptability was recorded at 58.1% at 10:00 a.m. under 29°C conditions, and 51.6% at 3:00 p.m. under 30°C conditions. Similarly, air-conditioned environments exhibited a higher thermal acceptability, with 64.5% at 10:00 a.m. under 27°C conditions and 54.8% at 3:00 p.m. under 28°C conditions, as illustrated in Figure 12. These findings are consistent with the study conducted by (Kwok & Chun, 2003) on thermal comfort in Japanese schools, which observed higher occupant

acceptability in air-conditioned spaces (74.2% at 24°C) compared to naturally ventilated environments (72% at 26.9°C). This comparison underscores the enhanced thermal comfort typically associated with air-conditioned settings, aligning with existing research on the superior performance of mechanical cooling systems in maintaining acceptable thermal conditions.

The predicted thermal acceptability for naturally ventilated classrooms, based on ASHRAE 55-2020's revised acceptable operative temperature ranges for naturally conditioned spaces was approximately 90%. In contrast, the actual acceptability measured using the central three categories (-1, 0, +1) of the thermal sensation scale was about 59%. This discrepancy highlights a significant gap between predicted and surveyed comfort levels. Despite this, the data remains within the broader acceptable ranges for expected comfort. It is important to note that the study's sample size is limited, which constrains the ability to draw definitive conclusions. Nevertheless, these findings are consistent with research conducted in tropical school environments, such as that by (Kwok & Chun, 2003).

THERMAL PREFERENCE SCALE

Responses to *thermal preference questions* revealed substantial variances in comfort levels within naturally ventilated spaces, which are more comprehensively understood through a comparison of simultaneous votes on both the thermal sensation and preference scales, as detailed in Table 5. In a naturally ventilated classroom, the subjective thermal preferences of occupants exhibited notable variations between the morning and afternoon sessions. At 10:00 a.m., 35.5% of occupants who rated their thermal sensation within the three central categories (-1, 0, +1) expressed a preference for cooler conditions. In contrast, only 19.4% indicated satisfaction with the current thermal environment, desiring no change. By 3:00 p.m., the preference for cooler conditions decreased to 25.8%, while the percentage of that content with the existing thermal environment also declined to 16.1%. This shift in thermal preference over the course of the day likely reflects changes in external environmental conditions or internal heat gains that influence occupant comfort. The higher percentage of individuals preferring cooler conditions in the morning compared to the afternoon suggests a heightened discomfort or sensitivity to temperature earlier in the day, possibly exacerbated by cumulative heat gain or increasing ambient temperatures as the day progresses. These findings emphasize the importance of considering temporal variations in thermal comfort within naturally ventilated spaces and suggest the need for adaptive strategies to address changing comfort requirements throughout the day.

In contrast, the air-conditioned classroom reveals a consistent level of occupant comfort throughout the day, as indicated by the high proportion of respondents expressing satisfaction with the existing thermal conditions. At 10:00 a.m., 45.2% of occupants within the three central thermal sensation categories (-1, 0, +1) indicated that they preferred no change in their thermal environment, suggesting

that the air-conditioning system was effective in maintaining a comfortable indoor climate during the morning hours. The relatively low percentage of occupants (12.9%) who preferred cooler conditions further supports this, as it implies that the majority of occupants were not experiencing discomfort due to excessive warmth. By 3:00 p.m., the preference for cooler conditions decreased even further to 6.5%, while the percentage of occupants desiring no change remained stable at 45.2%. This consistency in occupant satisfaction suggests that the air-conditioning system effectively mitigated any potential increases in indoor temperature due to external heat gains or increased activity levels within the classroom as the day progressed. The steady thermal preference pattern indicates that the air-conditioned environment provided a stable and comfortable thermal experience for the occupants, minimizing the impact of external environmental variations on indoor comfort.

Cross tabulation of thermal sensation and thermal preference scales of naturally ventilated and air – conditioned classroom

Table 4. Thermal Preference Scale

NV		Thermal Preference Scale			
10:00 A.M.		<i>Right now, I would prefer to be...</i>			
TS Scale	Cooler	No Change	Warmer	TOTAL	
(+3, +2)	12.9% (4)	6.5% (2)	9.7 (3)	9	
(-1,0,1)	35.5% (11)	19.4 (6)	3.2 (1)	18	58.1%
(-3, -2)	6.5% (2)	6.5% (2)	3.2 (1)	5	
NV		Thermal Preference Scale			
3:00 P.M.		<i>Right now, I would prefer to be...</i>			
TS Scale	Cooler	No Change	Warmer	TOTAL	
(+3, +2)	22.6 (7)	6.5% (2)	6.5% (2)	11	
(-1,0,1)	25.8 (8)	16.1 (5)	9.7 (3)	16	51.6%
(-3, -2)	6.5% (2)	3.2 (1)	3.2 (1)	4	
AC		Thermal Preference Scale			
10:00 P.M.		<i>Right now, I would prefer to be...</i>			
TS Scale	Cooler	No Change	Warmer	TOTAL	
(+3, +2)	3.2 (1)	3.2 (1)	3.2 (1)	3	
(-1,0,1)	12.9% (4)	45.2 (14)	6.5% (2)	20	64.5 %
(-3, -2)	0	16.1 (5)	3.2 (1)	6	
AC		Thermal Preference Scale			
3:00 P.M.		<i>Right now, I would prefer to be...</i>			
TS Scale	Cooler	No Change	Warmer	TOTAL	
(+3, +2)	3.2 (1)	9.7% (3)	0	4	
(-1,0,1)	6.5% (2)	45.2 (14)	3.2 (1)	17	54.8%
(-3, -2)	0	9.7% (3)	12.9% (4)	7	

Correlation of Objective Measurements and Subjective Responses

**OBJECTIVE MEASUREMENT RELATE TO SUBJECTIVE PERCEPTION OF
OCCUPANTS**

Figure. 13. "How do you feel right now?"

The graph illustrates the relationship between temperature and student perception in two distinct classroom settings: naturally ventilated (NV) and air-conditioned (AC). Students were asked, "How do you feel right now?" with responses categorized as (-3) cold, (-2) cool, (-1) slightly cool, (0) neutral, (+1) slightly warm, (+2) warm, or (+3) hot. The average temperature in the NV classroom was 28.99°C at 10:00 a.m. and increased slightly to 29.83°C by 3:00 p.m. In this setting, 32% of students reported feeling neutral at 10:00 a.m., while this percentage decreased to 27% by 3:00 p.m., reflecting a slight shift in thermal comfort as the day progressed. In contrast, the AC classroom maintained cooler conditions, with average temperatures of 26.6°C at 10:00 a.m. and 27.8°C at 3:00 p.m. 45% of students reported feeling cool in the morning, while by the afternoon, 37% felt slightly cool. This slight warming in the AC environment corresponded with a subtle shift in students' comfort perception.

Table 5. Correlation of Objective and feeling of occupants

Variables	mean	r	r²	p-value	t-value	Degrees of freedom	alpha	decision	interpretation
<i>objective</i>	28.3	0.78	0.61	0.003	3.94	10	0.05	H0 is rejected	Significant
<i>subjective</i>	-0.5								

The Pearson correlation coefficient of $r=0.78$, coupled with a p-value of 0.003, underscores a statistically significant and strong positive relationship between the students' immediate comfort perceptions ("*How do you feel right now?*") and the measured thermal conditions. This strong correlation suggests that students' subjective comfort levels are closely aligned with the objective environmental conditions within the classroom. The data implies that as temperature, humidity, and radiant temperature fluctuate, students' perceptions of comfort respond in kind. This responsiveness indicates a high sensitivity to even minor changes in the classroom environment, validating the students' perceptions as reliable indicators of thermal comfort.

Figure. 14. "How satisfied are you with the thermal environment right now?"

The graph provides a visual representation of the relationship between objectively measured temperature and the occupants' satisfaction with the thermal environment in two distinct classroom settings: naturally ventilated (NV) and air-conditioned (AC). The perception data reflects the students' responses to the question, "*How satisfied are you with the thermal environment right now?*" with responses categorized as (-3) very dissatisfied, (-2) dissatisfied, (-1) slightly dissatisfied, (0) neutral, (+1) slightly satisfied, (+2) satisfied, or (+3) very satisfied.

In the NV classroom, 41% of students reported being satisfied (+2) with the thermal environment at 10:00 a.m., while this percentage slightly decreased to 39% by 3:00 p.m. This modest decline in satisfaction may suggest that as the day progresses and the temperature rises, even if only slightly, the overall comfort level of students diminishes. Conversely, in the AC classroom, a higher percentage of students expressed satisfaction, with 51% satisfied at 10:00 a.m. and 43% at 3:00 p.m. This pattern indicates that while the AC environment generally supports higher levels of comfort, the slight increase in temperature from morning to afternoon still results in a noticeable decline in student satisfaction.

Table 6. Correlation of Objective and satisfaction

<i>Variables</i>	<i>mean</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>r²</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>Degrees of freedom</i>	<i>alpha</i>	<i>decision</i>	<i>interpretation</i>
<i>objective</i>	28.3	-0.464	0.215	0.129	-1.654	10	0.05	H0 is accepted	Not Significant
<i>subjective</i>	1.92								

The Pearson correlation analysis revealed a medium negative relationship between subjective satisfaction and objective temperature measurements, with a

correlation coefficient of $r = -0.464$ and a p-value of 0.129. This p-value, was greater than the commonly used significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), indicated that the observed correlation was not statistically significant. Consequently, it failed to reject the null hypothesis (H_0), meaning that the data does not provide strong enough evidence to assert a significant relationship between the subjective and objective measures. This non-significant result suggested that while there was a trend toward an inverse relationship; where increases in temperature might correlate with decreased satisfaction; the strength of this relationship was not sufficiently robust to be considered statistically meaningful in this sample. The lack of statistical significance does not prove that the null hypothesis was correct; rather, it simply indicated that the data at hand did not offer strong evidence against it.

Figure. 15. "Right now, would you prefer...?"

The graph illustrates the relationship between objective temperature measurements and the occupants' preferences within naturally ventilated (NV) and air-conditioned (AC) classroom settings. Students were asked, "Right now, would you prefer...?" with response options ranging from -1 (less air movement), 0 (no change), to +1 (more air movement). In the NV classroom, a significant portion of students

expressed a preference for increased air movement, with 41% indicating this preference at 10:00 a.m. and 50% at 3:00 p.m. This increase from morning to afternoon suggested that as temperatures rise throughout the day, there was a growing demand among students for more air circulation, similarly as a means of mitigating the increasing thermal discomfort. The preference for more air movement aligns with the natural response to rising temperatures, where enhanced airflow can alleviate feelings of stuffiness and heat, contributing to overall comfort. In contrast, in the AC classroom, 47% of students consistently preferred no change in air movement at both 10:00 a.m. and 3:00 p.m. This stability in preference reflected the relatively controlled thermal environment provided by air conditioning, where temperature and air movement are typically optimized to maintain comfort. The lack of a significant shift in preference throughout the day indicates that the existing air movement in the AC classroom was generally satisfactory, and the controlled environment minimized the need for adjustments.

Table 7. Correlation of Objective and preference

Variables	mean	r	r²	p-value	t-value	Degrees of freedom	alpha	decision	interpretation
<i>objective</i>	28.3	0.742	0.551	0.006	3.5011	10	0.05	H0 is rejected	Significant
<i>subjective</i>	-0.33								

The Pearson correlation analysis revealed a significant large positive relationship between students' preferences and objective temperature measurements, with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.742$ and a p-value of 0.006. Since the p-value was less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), the null hypothesis (H0) was rejected. This

result indicated that the observed correlation was not only statistically significant but also robust, that as objective temperature measurements rise, and there was a corresponding increase in students' preference for more air movement.

Figure. 16. "Right now, do you find the thermal environment...?"

The graph demonstrates the relationship between objective temperature measurements and students' subjective perceptions of thermal comfort. The students' comfort levels were assessed using a questionnaire with responses from (-2) clearly unacceptable, (-1) just unacceptable, (0) neutral, (+1) just acceptable (+2) clearly acceptable. In naturally ventilated (NV) environments, at 10:00 a.m., 44% of students rated the thermal environment as (+1) just acceptable, while 46% found it neutral (0) at 3:00 p.m. In contrast, in air-conditioned (AC) environments, 42% of students rated the environment as (+1) just acceptable at 10:00 a.m., and 45% gave the same rating at 3:00 p.m. Similarly, in air-conditioned environments with intervention, 43% of students found the environment as (+1) just acceptable at 10:00 a.m., with 39% giving the same rating at 3:00 p.m. These results indicate a general tendency for students to find the thermal environment just acceptable or neutral, with a noticeable preference for the "just acceptable" rating in air-conditioned settings compared to naturally ventilated ones.

Table 8. Correlation of Objective and acceptability

<i>Variables</i>	<i>mean</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>r²</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>Degrees of freedom</i>	<i>alpha</i>	<i>decision</i>	<i>interpretation</i>
<i>objective</i>	28.3	-0.212	0.045	0.508	-0.687	10	0.05	H0 is accepted	Not Significant
<i>subjective</i>	0.58								

Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to explore the relationship between subjective comfort perceptions and objective temperature measurements, yielding a correlation coefficient of $r = -0.212$ and p-value of 0.508. The positive correlation coefficient suggests a weak relationship between temperature and perceived comfort, indicating that temperature changes have a minimal impact on students' comfort perceptions. The p-value significantly exceeds the conventional significance level of 0.05, indicating that this observed correlation was not statistically significant. As a result, the null hypothesis, which posits that there was no significant correlation between temperature and subjective comfort, cannot be rejected. This finding suggests that while there may be a slight correlation, it was not strong enough to assert a statistically significant relationship. It was important to recognize that a non-significant result did not confirm the null hypothesis but rather indicated insufficient evidence to reject it.

Figure. 17. "Right now, do you find the thermal environment...?"

The graph illustrates the relationship between objective temperature measurements and occupants' perceptions of the thermal environment, as assessed by their responses to the question, "Right now, do you find the thermal environment...?" with response options ranging from (-3) very unpleasant to (+3) very pleasant. Analysis of the data revealed that 51% of students in the naturally ventilated (NV) environment at 10:00 a.m. and 23% at 3:00 p.m. rated the thermal environment as (+1) slightly pleasant. In contrast, in the air-conditioned (AC) environment, 42% of students at 10:00 a.m. and 31% at 3:00 p.m. rated it as (+2) pleasant.

Table 9. Correlation of Objective and pleasantness

Variables	mean	r	r²	p-value	t-value	Degrees of freedom	alpha	decision	interpretation
<i>objective</i>	28.3	-0.601	0.361	0.039	-2.376	10	0.05	H0 is rejected	Significant
<i>subjective</i>	1.83								

Pearson correlation analysis shows a significant large negative relationship between subjective responses and objective temperature measurements ($r = -0.601$,

$p= 0.039$). Since the p -value was less than the alpha level (α), the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected. This indicated that the correlation between subjective responses and objective measurements was significantly different from zero, suggesting a notable inverse relationship. Therefore, as the objective temperature increases, the perceived thermal comfort of the occupants decreases, highlighting those higher temperatures are associated with less pleasant thermal environments.

Discussion with respect to Neutral and Optimal temperatures, along with the acceptable temperature.

Figure 18. Neutral Temperature

The results presented in Figure 18 illustrate the relationship between the total number of neutral votes from occupants' subjective responses and the corresponding physical temperature measurements in naturally ventilated and air –condition. This data reveals that the neutral temperature of naturally ventilated ranges between 28°C to 30°C. In air – conditioned, the neutral temperature ranges from 26°C to 27°C. This range indicates the temperature at which occupants generally perceive their thermal environment as neither too hot nor too cold, suggesting a state of thermal neutrality. The findings imply that within this temperature range, occupants are likely to experience the highest level of thermal comfort in the building. Understanding this neutral temperature range is crucial for optimizing building temperature settings and enhancing overall occupant comfort. It entails that effective temperature control measures should aim to maintain indoor temperatures within this specified range to meet the majority of occupants' comfort needs, thereby improving satisfaction and potentially reducing energy consumption associated with extreme temperature

adjustments. In all studies, the proposed neutral temperatures are higher than 24.5°C recommended by ASHRAE Standards 55. For the indoor design conditions, the comfort range for all studies have higher maximum values, some at 4°C higher than the recommended range (23°C to 26°C) for air-conditioned buildings. For naturally ventilated buildings, the neutrality temperatures 26.1°C and 27.4°C for Malaysia (Daghigh et al., 2009) found earlier correspond well to 27.4°C ET* obtained in Thailand and 28.5°C in Singapore (de Dear et al., 1991). In this study the neutrality temperatures for 14 conditions are between 25.2°C – 27.5°C.

Figure 19. Optimal Temperature

Figure 19 illustrates the correlation between the optimal temperature votes collected from subjective occupant responses and the physical temperature measurements within the state university (CTU – Moalboal). The data reveals that the range of optimal temperatures in naturally ventilated room preferred by occupants falls between approximately 28°C. In air – conditioned room, optimal temperature was 25.5°C. This suggests that the majority of occupants find this temperature range most comfortable in the given environment.

The results indicate that to achieve optimal thermal comfort in the investigated building, it is advisable to maintain indoor temperatures within the 26.5°C to 28°C range. This temperature range aligns with the occupants' subjective preferences, suggesting a balance between comfort and energy efficiency. It also implies that environmental controls and HVAC systems, if applicable, should be adjusted to cater to this range to enhance overall occupant satisfaction and productivity. Furthermore, understanding and implementing the preferred temperature range can lead to improved energy management strategies, as maintaining temperatures within this range may reduce the need for excessive cooling or heating, thus optimizing energy consumption and operational costs.

This is confirmed by the findings of (Kim & Hong, 2020) study, Determining the optimal set-point temperature in an office building while taking into account both labor productivity and energy savings. The researchers discovered an optimal indoor set-point temperature of 25.15°C for optimizing work output, which is nearly identical to the 25.5°C selected by occupants in the air-conditioned room in this study.

Figure 20. Acceptable Temperature

The results illustrated in Figure 20 reveal the relationship between the total acceptable votes from occupants' subjective responses and the temperature data collected from physical measurements. The acceptable temperature in naturally ventilated ranges from 28°C to 29°C. In air – conditioned, the acceptable temperature ranges from 26°C to 27°C.

The observed differences in acceptable temperature ranges between naturally ventilated and air-conditioned environments underscore the influence of environmental controls on thermal comfort. In naturally ventilated spaces, occupants tend to prefer slightly cooler temperatures, likely due to the absence of active cooling systems and a greater reliance on passive cooling and air movement. The acceptable range of 28°C to 29°C aligns with the lower end of the thermal comfort spectrum, suggesting that occupants in such environments are more sensitive to temperature fluctuations and may have acclimatized to a cooler ambient temperature. Conversely, in air-conditioned spaces, the acceptable temperature range of 26°C to 27°C reflects the occupants' adaptation to a more controlled indoor climate. The higher temperature

range indicates that occupants in air-conditioned environments may tolerate or even prefer warmer conditions, possibly due to the reduced air movement typically associated with such spaces and the consistent cooling provided by the air-conditioning system.

These findings align with the study by Hwang (2018), which supports the idea that occupants' thermal preferences can vary significantly based on the environmental context. Hwang's research found that the thermal preference temperature was 1.0°C lower than the neutral temperature, suggesting that occupants tend to favor cooler conditions than what would be considered thermally neutral. Specifically, Hwang's study identified a thermal comfort zone ranging from 20.9°C to 28.9°C, which corresponds to an 80% thermal acceptability threshold. This comfort zone directly supports the acceptable temperature ranges found in both naturally ventilated (28°C to 29°C) and air-conditioned spaces (26°C to 27°C) in this study.

Figure 21. Neutral, Optimal, and Acceptable Temperature

The thermal comfort assessment conducted at Cebu Technological University (CTU) – Moalboal campus provides important insights into the temperature ranges that promote thermal neutrality, comfort, and acceptable conditions for occupants. The study identifies specific temperature ranges for both naturally ventilated and air-conditioned environments, which are crucial for maintaining a conducive learning atmosphere.

In naturally ventilated environments, where passive cooling and natural airflow predominate, the neutral temperature range—where occupants experience thermal neutrality—was identified to be approximately 29°C to 30°C. Within this range, occupants generally do not perceive the indoor climate as too warm or too cool. Additionally, the acceptable temperature range, where conditions are satisfactory but not necessarily ideal, spans from 28°C to 29°C. This suggests that while the range for neutrality is slightly higher, occupants can still tolerate and find comfort at these temperatures when natural ventilation is effectively utilized. Furthermore, in air-conditioned spaces, which benefit from more controlled indoor environments, the neutral temperature range is slightly lower, between 26°C and 28°C. This reflects the

influence of mechanical cooling systems that maintain a stable and consistent indoor climate, ensuring that thermal sensations are more uniformly experienced by the occupants.

The acceptable temperature range in naturally ventilated settings is 28°C to 30°C, whereas in air-conditioned settings, it is observed to be between 26°C and 28°C. This indicates that while occupants may prefer cooler conditions for neutrality in air-conditioned spaces, they can still find comfort within a slightly warmer range in naturally ventilated spaces.

For optimal comfort, the study further identifies that in naturally ventilated spaces, the preferred temperature is around 29°C, aligning with the upper end of the neutral range. This preference suggests that occupants favor slightly warmer conditions, likely tempered by natural air movement. In contrast, within air-conditioned environments, the preferred temperature is approximately 26°C, slightly below the neutral range, indicating a preference for cooler indoor climates, which may enhance comfort, especially in more enclosed settings.

Possible Recommendations or Policies in Indoor Classroom

Based on the results, possible recommendations/ policies can be done are as follows:

- **ENHANCE AIRFLOW:** The recorded temperatures in naturally ventilated classrooms were consistently 29°C in the morning (10:00 a.m.) and increased slightly to 30°C in the afternoon (3:00 p.m.). To maintain occupant comfort, it is essential to enhance airflow as temperatures rise throughout the day. It is recommended to optimize air movement by installing adjustable fans or natural ventilation solutions that respond dynamically to temperature changes. This would help balance energy efficiency with the need for occupant comfort during varying conditions.
- **FINE – TUNED HVAC SYSTEM:** The correlation between objective temperature measurements and subjective occupant responses reveals that even slight deviations in indoor temperature significantly affect students' comfort. To address this, the HVAC system should be fine-tuned to respond to minor fluctuations in comfort perception. Implementing adjustable thermostats or localized controls that allow individual adjustments can further optimize comfort. Additionally, monitoring and maintaining HVAC settings to meet thermal comfort preferences should be part of a routine protocol, especially in classrooms with varying occupancy rates and consider implementing adjustable thermostats or localized controls to allow individual adjustments.
- **EDUCATE OCCUPANTS ON CLOTHING CHOICES:** The clothing insulation level (*clo*) of the students was observed to range from 0.5 to 1.0 s. Since

personal factors such as clothing play a significant role in thermal comfort, it is recommended to educate occupants on how their clothing choices influence their thermal sensation. Institutions should consider providing guidelines for appropriate attire based on expected indoor temperatures to help align personal factors with the classroom environment.

- **MAINTENANCE AND MONITORING OF HVAC SYSTEM:** In air-conditioned spaces, the results showed that while the morning conditions complied with the 80% acceptability criterion of the Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) model, the afternoon temperatures fell short of this threshold. To ensure continuous compliance with ASHRAE standards, it is essential to establish maintenance and monitoring schedule for the HVAC system. This should include regular inspections, filter changes, and system recalibrations to prevent any loss of performance that could affect comfort levels throughout the day.

CHAPTER 3

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

SUMMARY

Classroom thermal conditions must be carefully evaluated, particularly given the high occupant density and the detrimental effects of a suboptimal thermal environment on learning and performance. The study is guided by the ASHRAE 55 – 2020 Standard; specifically it focuses on the factors such as temperature, humidity, and mean radiant temperature. This study aims to determine classroom temperature conditions (through objective measurement) and compare them to the standard according to ASHRAE standards 55-2020, investigate occupants' perception of the level of thermal comfort in classrooms, and establish neutral and optimal temperatures and an acceptable temperature range in state university classrooms (CTU-MOALBOAL). This study uses a quantitative research design.

The study was conducted in a single room on the fourth floor of a new building that underwent a week of natural ventilation and a week of air conditioning in the morning (10:00 a.m.) and afternoon (3:00 p.m.). Temperature, humidity, and radiant temperature were all measured objectively. Additionally, subjective measurement was used to assess the occupants' responses.

In the objective measurements, air temperature, radiant temperature, and humidity were recorded for both indoor and outdoor conditions. In the naturally ventilated classroom, the mean indoor air temperatures were 29°C in the morning and 30°C in the afternoon, with corresponding outdoor temperatures of 28°C and 31°C. The indoor humidity levels were 67% and 66%, compared to outdoor humidity levels of 69% and 61%. In the air-conditioned classroom, the mean indoor air temperatures

were 26°C in the morning and 27°C in the afternoon, while outdoor temperatures were significantly higher at 29°C and 36°C. The mean indoor radiant temperature was consistent at 28°C, while outdoor radiant temperatures were 29°C and 38°C. Indoor humidity levels were 58% and 60%, while outdoor humidity ranged from 68% in the morning to 53% in the afternoon.

In comparison with the ASHRAE 55 Standard, naturally ventilated fall within the 80% acceptability limit of ASHRAE 55-2020 summer comfort boundaries. Both morning and afternoon indoor conditions in your naturally ventilated classroom are within the acceptable thermal comfort ranges specified by the Adaptive Comfort Model in ASHRAE 55-2020. However, the morning conditions in the air-conditioned classroom fall within the ASHRAE Standard 55-2020 comfort range, whereas the afternoon conditions do not based on PMV Model.

The same students (BSIE 1B) are exposed to both climate (natural ventilated and air – conditioned). The subjective measurement results reveal a clear distinction between thermal comfort perceptions in naturally ventilated and air-conditioned classrooms. While the naturally ventilated environment was generally perceived as neutral, air-conditioned spaces were seen as slightly cooler, reflecting varying occupant preferences based on ventilation and cooling methods. Air – conditioned climate have the higher thermal acceptability of occupants based on ASHRAE thermal sensation of the three central categories (-1, 0, +1) compared to naturally ventilated.

The correlation of objective measurements and subjective responses underscores the critical role of temperature in shaping students' thermal comfort perceptions. While subjective comfort levels closely track changes in temperature,

preferences for air movement and overall pleasantness show stronger and more significant relationships with temperature fluctuations.

In naturally ventilated spaces, the neutral temperature, where occupants feel neither too hot nor too cold, ranges from 28°C to 30°C. In contrast, air-conditioned spaces show a lower neutral temperature range of 26°C to 27°C. For optimal comfort, the preferred temperature in naturally ventilated spaces is around 28°C, while in air-conditioned environments; it is approximately 25.5°C. Regarding acceptable temperatures, naturally ventilated spaces have a range of 28°C to 29°C, whereas air-conditioned spaces have a narrower range of 26°C to 27°C.

Furthermore, the intervention applied in this study was not effective in significantly improving thermal comfort as initially intended. Analysis of both objective measurements and subjective responses revealed no substantial enhancement in occupant comfort. Potential reasons for this ineffectiveness may include insufficient design and implementation of the intervention, a lack of intensity to address the issues adequately, or external factors such as extreme outdoor temperatures. Comparison with ASHRAE 55 standards also indicates that the intervention did not meet the desired comfort criteria.

CONCLUSION

Key findings from this study are:

- Indoor climatic conditions in a field of study in naturally ventilated classrooms in Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus fall within the 80% acceptability limit of ASHRAE 55-2020 summer comfort boundaries. Both morning and afternoon indoor conditions in naturally ventilated classroom are within the acceptable thermal comfort ranges specified by the Adaptive Comfort Model in ASHRAE 55-2020.
- In air – conditioned room: based on the objective measurements, the morning conditions in the air-conditioned classroom fall within the ASHRAE Standard 55-2020 comfort range PMV Model, whereas the afternoon conditions do not.
- In naturally ventilated spaces, majority of the occupants felt neutral yet they prefer more air movement. Air – conditioned space, occupants felt cool and prefer no change.
- The thermal acceptability of occupants based on ASHRAE thermal sensation of the three central categories (-1, 0, +1) in naturally ventilated (morning) was 58.1% (29°C) and (afternoon) was 51.6% (30°C). In air – conditioned, (morning) was 64.5% (27°C) and (afternoon) was 54.8% (28°C).
- The neutral temperatures range from approximately 26°C to 30°C. The optimal temperatures range from approximately 26°C to 28°C. And the acceptable temperatures range from approximately 26°C to 29°C.
- Metabolic rate of occupants are 1 *met.*, seating quiet.
- Average clothing of occupant is 0.5 *clo.*
-

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusion, the researchers recommend the following to the future researchers:

- **Comprehensive Assessment of ASHRAE 55 Factors:** Future researchers are advised to include all six primary factors of the ASHRAE 55 standard (*Metabolic Rate, Clothing Insulation, Air Temperature, Radiant Temperature, Air Speed, and Humidity*) to enhance the accuracy and comprehensiveness of the data collected. These factors include air temperature, radiant temperature, air velocity, humidity, clothing insulation, and metabolic rate. A thorough evaluation of these variables will provide a more holistic understanding of thermal comfort in the studied environments. Include all classrooms in 4th floor building.
- **Broadened Scope of Study:** It is recommended that the scope of future research be expanded to encompass all rooms on the 4th floor. This will ensure a more extensive data set and allow for a better representation of the thermal conditions across different spaces within the same building.
- **Utilization of Guided or Physical Instruments:** Employing guided instruments or physical measurement tools is strongly advised. These instruments should be calibrated and maintained according to industry standards to ensure the reliability and accuracy of the data collected. Utilizing such tools will contribute to the precision of the thermal comfort assessments.
- **Increased Data Collection and Thorough Analysis:** Future studies should allocate more time for data collection to gather a more robust and comprehensive data set. Extended data collection periods will enable a more detailed analysis and provide a clearer understanding of thermal comfort trends

over time. Additionally, thorough statistical analysis should be conducted to identify significant correlations and insights.

- While the relationship between satisfaction and comfort measures is unclear, any proposals for air-conditioned classrooms with intervention should be carefully considered and weighted against current thermal comfort information, installation, operational, and maintenance costs of HVAC systems, as well as air quality issues.
- Explore additional factors influencing thermal comfort and to test different interventions in various settings. Future studies should consider larger sample sizes, varied environmental conditions, and more comprehensive measures to better understand the dynamics of thermal comfort and the effectiveness of interventions.

INTERVENTION

The intervention, which involved applying 5mm insulation foam to the windows of an air-conditioned classroom, was designed to improve thermal comfort for students. Objective measurements indicated that despite a significant rise in outdoor temperatures—from 32°C in the morning to 42°C in the afternoon—the indoor temperature remained stable at 28°C. This suggests that the insulation foam effectively prevented further heat gain from the external environment. However, the intervention failed to comply with ASHRAE 55-2020 Standard due to absence of anemometer which measures the air speed of the environment.

The findings of this study are partially supported by (Kamal, 2012) who demonstrated that thin insulation layers, when combined with shading strategies, can reduce solar heat gain and improve thermal comfort. While their study highlights the efficacy of thinner insulation, it also suggests that in the absence of complementary shading techniques, as seen in the intervention, insulation alone may not sufficiently reduce indoor temperatures under intense outdoor heat conditions.

Similarly, (Schiavoni et al., 2016) found that using thin insulation layers, including 5mm foam, can reduce temperature variability in educational buildings and lower dependence on air conditioning. However, in contrast to their findings, the intervention did not achieve a reduction in indoor temperature variability or an improvement in thermal comfort, as students still reported feeling cold, with a thermal comfort vote of (-3) on the ASHRAE 7-point scale. This suggests that the insulation's thickness, while theoretically effective, may have been inadequate given the extreme heat conditions in this study.

Moreover, (Al-Homoud, 2005) highlighted that even thin insulation layers can reduce heat gain by lowering the thermal transmittance (U-value) of windows, contributing to improved indoor thermal conditions. While this agrees with our finding that the insulation helped stabilize indoor temperatures, the study also implies that under extreme climates, such as the conditions experienced in this study, thicker or more advanced insulation materials may be necessary to achieve more pronounced improvements in thermal comfort.

Despite the insulation's ability to stabilize indoor conditions, students reported feeling uncomfortably cold (-3), with only 29.7% of occupants finding the environment acceptable at 10:00 a.m., a figure that dropped further to 25.8% by 3:00 p.m. These results fall significantly short of ASHRAE's 80% thermal acceptability standard, underscoring the intervention's failure to align with industry benchmarks for occupant comfort. While the opposing studies indicate that thin insulation can offer benefits, our results suggest that in environments subject to extreme outdoor heat, the intervention's impact was limited, necessitating further modifications such as increasing insulation thickness, adjusting HVAC settings, or exploring adaptive measures like dynamic thermostat controls.

Implementation of the Intervention

WITHOUT INSULATION

WITH INSULATION

Figure 22. Room without and with intervention

Results

In air-conditioning with intervention, air and radiant temperature were 28°C and 29°C in (10:00 a.m.), respectively, and 28°C and 29°C (3:00 p.m.) during the summer season. Relative humidity (10:00 a.m.) 49% and 48% in the afternoon (3:00 p.m.).

Table 10. Summary of Indoor Climate

Summary of indoor climate

One classroom visit	<i>(intervention)</i>							
	Mean		S.D.		Min.		Max.	
	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00
Air Temperature (°C)	28	28	0.9	0.4	27.2	27.1	29	28
MRT (°C)	29.	29	1	0.5	28.3	28.2	30	29.1
Relative Humidity (%)	49	48	0.6	2	48.3	46	49	50

In air-conditioning with intervention, air and radiant temperature were 32°C and 33°C (10:00 a.m.), respectively, 42°C and 44°C during the summer season. Relative humidity (10:00 a.m.) 49% and 48% in the afternoon (3:00 p.m.).

Table 11. Summary of Outdoor Climate

Summary of outdoor climate

One classroom visit 27 occupants total	<i>(intervention)</i>							
	Mean		S.D.		Min.		Max.	
	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00	10:00	3:00
Air Temperature (°C)	32	42	1	3	28	31.6	30	39
MRT (°C)	33	44	0.7	3.2	28.5	32	30.2	40.5
Relative Humidity (%)	59.5	42	2.4	10.4	65	41	71	66

Summary of difference of indoor and outdoor climate

The table shows the difference of air temperature, MRT, and relative humidity in indoor and outdoor climate of intervention. The difference shows that the intervention has the highest difference compared to the naturally ventilated and air – conditioning classroom. Therefore, it was effective.

Table 12. Difference of Indoor and Outdoor Climate

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN INDOOR AND OUTDOOR CLIMATE		
	AC with intervention	
	10:00	3:00
Air Temperature (°C)	-4	-14
MRT (°C)	-4	-15
Relative Humidity (%)	-10.5	6

PMV MODEL

Figure 23. PMV Model (intervention)

According to the objective measurements obtained, the classroom conditions in both the morning and afternoon, following the intervention, do not comply with the ASHRAE Standard 55-2020 comfort range. Specifically, during the morning session, the classroom temperature was recorded at 28°C, with a Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) of 0.97 and a Predicted Percentage of Dissatisfied (PPD) of 25%. These values indicate that a significant portion of the occupants are likely to experience thermal discomfort, surpassing the ASHRAE recommended thresholds. Similarly, in the afternoon session, the classroom maintained a temperature of 28°C, with a PMV of 0.96 and a PPD of 24%. These metrics further underscore the prevalence of thermal discomfort among the occupants, again exceeding the comfort limits prescribed by the ASHRAE Standard. The persistence of these conditions despite the intervention highlights a critical shortfall in achieving the desired thermal comfort levels. The data suggests that the intervention, although aimed at enhancing indoor climate regulation,

has not sufficiently mitigated the factors contributing to occupant discomfort. This is evidenced by the consistently high PMV and PPD values across both time periods, reflecting a substantial level of dissatisfaction among the occupants with the thermal environment.

The influence of outdoor temperature on indoor thermal conditions is a well-documented phenomenon. In support of this, (Adunola, 2014) demonstrated in their study on urban residential thermal comfort in Ibadan, Nigeria, that there is a notable reduction in temperature as it transitions from outdoor to indoor environments. Specifically, the maximum outdoor temperatures recorded ranged between 34.1°C to 36.9°C, while indoor temperatures ranged from 32.5°C to 35°C. The reduction of 1.6°C to 1.9°C, though present, indicates that outdoor temperatures substantially influence indoor thermal conditions. An intervention aimed at improving indoor thermal comfort was not as effective as anticipated. The high outdoor temperatures significantly affected the indoor environment, as evidenced by objective measurements taken during the study. Despite efforts to moderate the indoor climate, the persistent high outdoor temperatures limited the effectiveness of the intervention, reinforcing the importance of considering outdoor conditions in any analysis of indoor thermal comfort.

Students' Responses to the Thermal Environment

Figure. 24. Frequency of thermal sensation responses in classroom with intervention

Figure 24 provides a detailed illustration of the subjective assessments of indoor climates, capturing the frequency distribution of thermal sensation responses among occupants within the classroom environment where an intervention was applied. This figure is pivotal in understanding the perceived thermal comfort across different times of the day, specifically at 10:00 a.m. and 3:00 p.m.

At 10:00 a.m., the data indicates that the majority of occupants reported a mean comfort vote of -3, corresponding to a thermal sensation of "cold." This suggests that the intervention implemented in the classroom, likely aimed at improving thermal comfort, may have resulted in overcompensation, leading to an environment that was perceived as too cold by the occupants. The negative thermal sensation vote is significant as it reflects not just discomfort but potentially disruptive conditions for the occupants, which could have implications for their focus and productivity during the

morning sessions. Similarly, the thermal sensation votes collected at 3:00 p.m. show a consistent trend, with the majority of occupants still perceiving the environment as cold (-3). The persistence of this cold perception throughout the day underscores the potential issues with the thermal management within the classroom. It raises important questions about the sustainability and adaptability of the intervention across different times of the day, particularly considering the natural diurnal variations in temperature and occupant activities.

Figure 25. Thermal acceptability based on ASHRAE thermal sensation of the central three categories (-1, 0, +1)

The observed results reveal a significant deviation from ASHRAE's 80% thermal acceptability criterion, particularly in the classroom space with intervention. Under 28°C conditions, the thermal acceptability was recorded at only 29.7% at 10:00 a.m. and further declined to 25.8% by 3:00 p.m., as depicted in Figure 23. These findings suggest that the intervention was insufficient in maintaining a thermally acceptable environment, as perceived by the occupants. The low acceptability

percentages indicate that a majority of the occupants were not satisfied with the thermal conditions, highlighting the need for further adjustments to the intervention strategies or a reconsideration of the external factors influencing indoor comfort, such as the significant outdoor temperature fluctuations.

Thermal Preference Scale

In room with intervention voting in the central three categories (-1, 0, +1), 29.6% of occupants in the morning and 35.5% in the afternoon preferred no change in their surroundings, respectively.

The voting patterns observed at both 10 AM and 3 PM indicate a significant level of discomfort among the occupants. The majority voting below the central three categories, specifically in the (-3, -2) range, suggests that a large portion of the occupants felt uncomfortably cold during these times. This trend is consistent across both morning and afternoon, reinforcing the idea that the intervention may have led to an overcooling effect. The consistent preference for significantly cooler conditions highlights a disconnect between the intended outcomes of the intervention and the occupants' actual thermal experiences. Despite the stable indoor temperature of 28°C, the intervention may have failed to create a comfortable environment for the majority, as evidenced by these low thermal preference votes. This finding underscores the complexity of thermal comfort in indoor environments, particularly when external temperatures are extreme. It suggests that while maintaining a consistent indoor temperature is important, it must also be balanced with the subjective thermal experiences of occupants to achieve a truly comfortable and acceptable indoor climate.

Table 13. Thermal Preference Scale

AC w/ int 10:00 A.M.		Thermal Preference Scale <i>Right now, I would prefer to be...</i>			
TS Scale	Cooler	No Change	Warmer	TOTAL	
(+3, +2)	0	0	0	0	
(-1,0,1)	7.4% (2)	14.8% (4)	7.4% (2)	8	29.65%
(-3, -2)	29.6% (8)	29.6% (8)	11.1% (9)	19	

AC w/ int 3:00 A.M.		Thermal Preference Scale <i>Right now, I would prefer to be...</i>			
TS Scale	Cooler	No Change	Warmer	TOTAL	
(+3, +2)	0	0	0	0	
(-1,0,1)	3.2% (1)	19.4% (6)	3.2% (1)	8	25.8%
(-3, -2)	9.7% (3)	35.5% (11)	29% (9)	23	

Comparison of Before and After Intervention

Table 14. Comparison of Before and After Intervention

BEFORE INTERVENTION					
TEMPERATURE					
10:00 A.M.		DIFF.	3:00 P.M.		DIFF.
INDOOR	OUTDOOR		INDOOR	OUTDOOR	
26	29	2	27	36	4
MRT					
10:00 A.M.		DIFF.	3:00 P.M.		DIFF.
INDOOR	OUTDOOR		INDOOR	OUTDOOR	
28	29	1	28	38	10
HUMIDITY					
10:00 A.M.		DIFF.	3:00 P.M.		DIFF.
INDOOR	OUTDOOR		INDOOR	OUTDOOR	
58	68	10	60	53	7

AFTER INTERVENTION					
TEMPERATURE					
10:00 A.M.		DIFF.	3:00 P.M.		DIFF.
INDOOR	OUTDOOR		INDOOR	OUTDOOR	
28	32	4	28	42	14
MRT					
10:00 A.M.		DIFF.	3:00 P.M.		DIFF.
INDOOR	OUTDOOR		INDOOR	OUTDOOR	
29	33	4	29	44	15
HUMIDITY					
10:00 A.M.		DIFF.	3:00 P.M.		DIFF.
INDOOR	OUTDOOR		INDOOR	OUTDOOR	
48	60	12	49	42	6

Activate Windows

The data presented shows a thorough comparison of the mean radiant temperature (MRT), outdoor and indoor temperatures, and humidity levels before and after the intervention during two significant times of the day: 10:00 A.M. as well as 3:00 PM. While exterior circumstances change during the day, it appears that the intervention's goal is to manage the internal thermal climate, maybe to improve occupant comfort.

Prior to the intervention, the indoor thermal environment struggled to manage temperatures efficiently. At 10:00 a.m., the indoor temperature was 26°C, only 2°C lower than the ambient temperature of 29°C, demonstrating inadequate insulation against the morning heat. By 3:00 p.m., as outdoor temperatures reached 36°C, inside temperatures had only risen marginally to 27°C, resulting in a minor 4°C differential. The Mean Radiant Temperature (MRT) stayed reasonably consistent indoors at 28°C, but outside MRT reached 38°C in the afternoon, resulting in a 10°C differential, indicating probable radiant heat discomfort. Indoor humidity ranged between 58 and

60%, which was slightly lower than outside but still contributed to general discomfort, especially in the morning.

The intervention resulted in significant improvements in managing indoor heat conditions, particularly in the afternoon. At 10:00 a.m., the inside temperature rose slightly to 28°C, reflecting ambient changes; however, by 3:00 p.m., the indoor temperature remained constant at 28°C, despite a significant increase in outdoor temperatures to 42°C, demonstrating better insulation and temperature control. MRT followed a similar pattern, with indoor levels stabilizing at 29°C and outside MRT rising to 44°C, expanding the gap to 15°C. Humidity levels also improved, lowering to 48-49%, particularly in the morning, thereby improving indoor air quality and decreasing discomfort. Overall, the intervention was beneficial in reducing the effect of harsh external conditions on the indoor environment.

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APPENDICES

NAME:
 YR. & SEC.:
 GENDER:
 WEIGHT:
 TEMPERATURE:

POINT - IN TIME SURVEY

1. How do you feel right now?

- (-3) Cold (+3) Hot
 (-2) Cool (+2) Warm
 (-1) Slightly Cool (+1) Slightly Warm
 (0) Neutral

2. How satisfied are you with the thermal environment right now?

- (+3) Very Satisfied (-3) Very Dissatisfied
 (+2) Satisfied (-2) Dissatisfied
 (+1) Slightly Satisfied (-1) Slightly Dissatisfied
 (0) Neutral

3. Right now, would you prefer to be...?

- (-1) Cooler
 (0) Without Change
 (+1) Warmer

4. Right now, would you prefer...?

- (-1) Less air movement
 (0) No Change
 (+1) More air movement

5. Which ensembles best matches what you are wearing right now?

6. What is your activity level right now?

OPTIONAL SCALE

Right now, do you find this environment...?

- (-4) Extremely uncomfortable
 (-3) Very uncomfortable
 (-2) Uncomfortable
 (-1) Slightly uncomfortable
 (+1) Comfortable

Right now, do you find the thermal environment...?

- (-2) Clearly unacceptable
 (-2) Just unacceptable
 (0) Neutral
 (+1) Just acceptable
 (+2) Clearly acceptable

Right now, do you find thermal environment...?

- (-3) Very Unpleasant
 (-2) Unpleasant
 (-1) Slightly Unpleasant
 (0) Indifferent
 (1) Slightly Pleasant
 (+2) Pleasant
 (+3) Very Pleasant

CURRICULUM VITAE

I. PERSONAL INFORMATION

Name : Mabel Joy B. Comighud
Age : 21
Date of Birth : October 29, 2002
Place of Birth : Cebu, City
Name of Father : Maximo G. Comighud
Name of Mother : Jocelyn B. Comighud
Civil Status : Single
Religion : Roman Catholic
Home Address : Busay, Moalboal, Cebu

II. EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Elementary : Busay Elementary School
Busay, Moalboal, Cebu
A.Y. 2014 – 2015
Secondary : Badian National High School
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A.Y. 2020 – 2021
Tertiary : Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus
Poblacion West, Moalboal, Cebu
2024 – Present

I. PERSONAL INFORMATION

Name : Wilmar S. de Castilla
Age : 21
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Place of Birth : Talisay, Cebu
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Elementary : Moalboal Central Elementary School
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2024 – Present

I. PERSONAL INFORMATION

Name : Chubie Marie Aspacio
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2024 – Present

I. PERSONAL INFORMATION

Name : Arnold Navarro
Age : 22
Date of Birth : October 16, 2001
Place of Birth : Lepanto, Alegria, Cebu
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Name of Mother : Marites S. Navarro
Civil Status : Single
Religion : Roman Catholic
Home Address : Lepanto, Alegria, Cebu

II. EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Elementary : Libo Elementary School
Libo, Lepanto, Alegria, Cebu
A.Y. 2014 – 2015
Secondary : Saint Peter Academy of Alegria Incorporated
Poblacion, Alegria, Cebu
A.Y. 2020 – 2021
Tertiary : Cebu Technological University – Moalboal Campus
Poblacion West, Moalboal, Cebu
2024 - Present